

Local, homegrown terrorism and organized crime in the Western societies.

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The report views terrorism as a local, homegrown problem of the members of the West, as a society phenomenon and compares it with the organized crime through the prism of social and criminal psychology. Without giving any pretense to exhaustiveness or depth, the report also makes a psychological analysis of the personalities of individuals engaged in criminal, whether terrorist or organized criminal activity.

Keywords: *terrorism, crime, radicalization, psychology, analysis*

OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN EUROPE AND WESTERN SOCIETIES

In the modern world of a globalized economies, societies, open European borders, technologies and information, one thing remains unchanged - the man in its nature and wholeness. **The personality**, which, according to psychology, constitutes of the individual way of thinking, feeling and acting¹⁹ **remains unchanged**. Interaction and environment are different depending on geography, confessions, historical and cultural values, norms of the respective society in which the individual has grown up and has been civilized. Of course, every individual, each person has a life cycle, but **the cultural - historical rules, norms and values are constant, although changing, as the constant is the resetting of the process of personality development in death and its development from initium novum* in the new life . The collective human, historical spirit of every society is passed on precisely in its mechanisms of building the individual, his schooling, education and his present functioning to each of his newly born members.**

The active shooters, terrorist cells, organizations and their members, the professional criminals - traffickers, assassins, organized crime groups (henceforth, OCG) are personalities, in psychological context, individuals from our collective communities, linked by common political and ideological similarities and interests as we are. They come from the same societies of law-abiding and altruistic citizens who aim to change their environment of living for the better and/or to achieve financial wealth and success for them and their own countries and societies with the instruments available for all of us within these very same countries and societies. Everybody strives to fulfill his personal needs and everybody starts his life journey with different social-economic status. As some of us strive, others don't, the question is what tools each of us use and did they harm other and/or trespass the laws of the state. Under comparable conditions, we have different results, of course - the free will of each person plays

*initium novum – from latin, means new beginning

¹⁹ Cacioppo, J., Freberg, L., Discovering Psychology, 2015

the decisive role and has the last word, but one is certain and it is that the general object and subject of activity of terrorist organizations and individual terrorists as well as organized crime groups and their members are our societies. The same societies that have tutored and created them, who gave them the opportunity and the environment to be what they have chosen to be. To form themselves as criminals or terrorists, willingly or not, and to exploit us and our societies for resources to supply their criminal and terror activities.

Here we do not talk about the exported terrorism of the 20th and 19th centuries, mainly originating from the local nationalism and state to state politics, where members of an organization or state are carrying out a subversive activity to the neighboring one in order to achieve economic, political, social or other interests. We observe and subject the contrary, terrorists grown and raised by their and our own – common for the victims and perpetrator countries. Citizens who are part of terrorist groups (henceforth TG) and members of criminal groups that have made the conscious choice to be professional criminals against their own societies who they deny, exploit and use to achieve their criminal or terrorist purposes.

We must see the fight, as it is between cultural and social differences, where objects are not separate states, but ideologies and social norms and classes. Such a comparison can be made between the manifestations of the so-called radical, white nationalists and the statements of so-called extreme Islamists and radical jihadists, where we see the ideological postulates of white internationalism uniting all white nationalists and the Islam, who unites all the "righteous" muslims and divides them into their righteousness against all kafirs (from arabic, infidels). In both cases, we have a global conflict between ideas of globalized ideologies who does not have a single flag and a state, who are united not on the public sign of the nation and society, but on the conceptual idea of an ideology that does not respect boundaries and states, and whose target is the West and its citizens, states and societies with their cultural, social norms and political freedoms.

Equivalent is the situation with organized crime, where the ideology among members can easily be found in the popular postulates on the topic and it is most easily expressed through its main goal - acquiring money - the economic rise at any cost without respecting and obeying the law, the freedom of others and social and public norms.

LOCAL, HOMEGROWN TERRORISM AND THE ORGANIZED CRIME

For the purposes of the present work, in the term terrorism we should understand "***an activity that (1) involves a violent act or an act dangerous to human life, property, or infrastructure; and (2) appears to be intended to intimidate or coerce a civilian population; to influence the policy of a government by intimidation or coercion; or to affect the conduct of a government by mass destruction, assassination, kidnapping, or hostage-taking***"¹¹, which is the US Department of State definition. The author recalls that there are over 100

¹¹US Department of State, BUREAU OF COUNTERTERRORISM, Executive Order 13224, 2001

definitions of terrorism and not one officially, unified, well-established by all nations on a global scale definition. The same problem - the lack of a clear definition, unified and internationally accepted stands before the definition of organized crime and organized crime groups. For the purposes of this paper, we will use the United Nations definition of an organized criminal group - *"a group of three or more individuals that is not randomly formed, exists for a period of time and acts to perform at least one punishable by law crime for a period of more than four years, with the purpose of obtaining, directly or indirectly, financial or other material benefit."*¹⁸

In this section we will look at the relationship between terrorist organizations and crime as well as the social characteristics and individualities of today's terrorism in the West and its perpetrators. The main events of local, homegrown terrorism in Europe and Western societies in recent years are the events in France, Germany, the United Kingdom and Spain between 2015 and 2017, where eight terrorist acts were committed with 349 murders and over 1 500 injured.¹ For example we will also use the terrorist acts committed by the active shooters, such as the Anders Breivik in Norway, which killed 77 people and injured more than 300² and Brenton Harrison Tarrant from Christchurch, New Zealand, where 50 people died and over 40 were injured.³

The purpose of the terms homegrown and local, which are describing terrorism in the present work is to describe the origin and socio-demographic characteristics of the terrorists who performed these acts. Despite their membership of international terrorist organizations or the sharing of radical ideas, the shooters Anders Breivik and the Christchurch shooter share the origin and nationality of the country whose citizens they were attacking. Same model is represented with other terrorists, but this time motivated by Jihad ideology who were also citizens of the countries they attack. Terrorist who committed the violent acts of November 2015 in Paris, France⁴, the heavy truck attack in Nice, France⁵ and others ... are people with French citizenship and has had lived and raised in the attacked countries for years. More detailed presentation and factology is not the subject of the present study, but the current work relies to the authors of the study **"Jihadi terrorists in Europe: their characteristics and the circumstances in which they have joined the Jihad: an exploratory study"** which concludes that **"A significant part of these persons of non-European extraction, however, have been born and raised in Europe: i.e. the group of second and third generation migrants."**⁶

This was the case of 56 out of the 146 cases in which we could determine the country in which the jihadi terrorists grew up." and "Looking at place of residence, the overwhelming majority of the jihadi terrorists in our sample are residents of a European country (211 out of 219 persons). As mentioned above, more than a third of them have been (born and) raised in these countries. Others have been living for more than ten years in a European country"⁶.

The same conclusion is reached also by P. Bergen, CNN National Security Analyst, who concludes that **"every lethal terrorist attack in the United States since 9/11 has been carried out by an American citizen or a legal permanent resident."**⁷

¹⁸United Nations – office of drugs and crime, UN convention against transnational organized crime and the protocols thereto, 2004

⁶ Bakker, E., Jihadi terrorists in Europe, NETHERLANDS INSTITUTE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS - Clingendael, 2006 3

⁷ Bergen, P., "Bergen: A pattern in terror -- second generation, homegrown", CNN, 2017

The author of the present study came to the same conclusion in his science report "Analysis of active shooter incidents", where all applied and analyzed cases of active shooters in the United States were born and raised in the American society and where the case of terrorism in Europe and the world is explored again in the context of the active shooter method and tactic. In this sense, domestic, homegrown terrorists on the territory of the United States, on the basis of their motivation, may be divided into two types:

Ideologically motivated. These are all cases falling within the section of the presently described terrorists, where the perpetrators are motivated by a radical ideology aimed at influencing a wide audience. An ideology that is shared by themselves due to different individual and personality traits. This is the case with Omar Matten, who killed 49 people at a nightclub in Orlando, USA, who identified himself as a "Soldier of Allah"⁸.

Pathologically motivated. These are all cases of violence committed because of obvious personally motivated character deviations, such as a desire for revenge, personal aggression, compensatory desires for self-affirmation, power, glory, etc. These are all personal deviations, pathological patterns classified by psychology and ICD-10 (the international classification of diseases) as psychological disorders. Such an example is Maurice Clemens, who killed 4 people in 2009 - 5 weeks before his murders, a court-appointed health assessment had been issued that describes Clemens hallucinating as "people drinking blood and eating babies like cannibals in streets without laws"⁹.

Investigating the criminal element and the links of terrorism with crime, it should be noted that 38 of the 76 people involved in the terrorist acts in France for the period had a criminal record of previous arrests and criminal acts - 28 of these perpetrators had been convicted before 2015 and 27 had been serving prison sentences. A total of 15 had been in a situation of severe relapse with more than one law violation and multiple detentions, repeating the offense acts and 16 of all future terrorists, had criminal registrations and history of participation in combat actions in foreign territories.¹⁰

The attached data show that today's terrorists who are attacking the Western societies come from the societies themselves. In cases where they profess the ideology of radical Islam, they are 2nd, 3rd generation migrants or have been resident for at least 10 years in the country which they attack and their family and background are from non-European / Western countries. In the cases of the so-called white nationalists, professing a radical ideology, they were also born and raised, originating from the country target of their attack. In the case of pathological personality disorders and deviations, terrorists are even closer to the object of their attack due to personal connections and directed compensatory relations to the victims target group, and they are also nationals of the target countries.

On the first look, the pathologically motivated perpetrators lack one of the main aspects of the US Department of State definition - political motivation. On second look, their deeds are connected to their micro sociological climate of power politics of groups or institutions, either it is a local school, military base, private sector company etc. In that matter we can consider that the ideologically motivated perpetrators try to affect the power dynamics of a whole political system or a country and pathologically motivated perpetrators are trying

⁸ Bergen, P., "Bergen: A pattern in terror -- second generation, homegrown", CNN, 2017

⁹ Atanasov, A., "Analysis of active shooter incidents, AMoI, 2017

¹⁰ GLOBSEC, Colomina, P., France, O., Saverot, D., "FROM CRIMINALS TO TERRORISTS AND BACK?" Quarterly report: France. 2017

to influence the same matter in a more domestic, local aspect of a city, society group or representation of an institution. Some of these cases, based on the specific circumstances of the crime can be defined as a manslaughter in especially large size or other juridical term from the affected country, but the thin psychological line here is the radicalisation, motivation and execution, where both of the described groups stand on identical manner and models.

In the majority of the cases, the perpetrators have previous criminal offenses and a clear history of a violation of the law, all of whom have a personal motive linked to their specific idea of the world, which is associated to their personal being. Like example, this is clearly expressed by Anders Breivik who had unsuccessfully applied in the army and also in the majority, almost all cases of pathologically motivated terrorists. Investigating the 76 terrorists in France, **56% of them were unemployed at the time of their arrest, and 63% of them had secondary education as the highest level of education**¹⁰. These data put them in the commonly accepted criteria for risk profile for committing crimes and norms used in profiling persons in the conventional crime, where the same problems in social and public adaptation are observed. Some exceptions are made by the cases of white nationalists, where both cited before perpetrators (Christchurch shooter and A. Breivik) have permanent income and funds to fund themselves, their terrorist acts and interests.

In conclusion to this chapter, we have to say that although they are part of our society, perpetrators of terrorist acts do not share the same values, interests and ideologies that we share and do not adapt to our society successfully. This is also the case with criminal groups and criminals doing criminal activity as a means of self-assertion in society, income and career. These people are choosing the social role of a criminal and associated it with their personality. The role of the criminal is, by its very nature, socially dangerous and is a form of social radicalization because it victimizes and directs the personal aggression and methods of survival against the weak individuals of the society from which resources can be extracted by force, instead of contributing to the given society and receiving a reward for it (such as working and taking a salary).

The criminal deprives the society of his goods without respecting social norms, through violence for personal gain, contributing nothing. A similar psychic process also occurs in the mental worlds of terrorist perpetrators, where society is victimized and offended by the abuser because of his sense of personal and ideological right that he imposes on the defenseless and vulnerable members to gain a sense of satisfaction. Either rightness or justness, martyrdom (in the name of Allah, for example), glory or political, financial benefits for him or the organization the perpetrator represents.

The subject of analysis and research is whether it is non-adaptation process that precedes the radicalization process - or - radicalization precedes the process of non-adaptation. **In both cases, modern perpetrators of terrorist acts and criminal acts in the Western societies have grown up among us, educated and built by the same state and homogeneous mass of people of which we are part too.**

¹⁰ GLOBSEC, Colomina, P., France, O., Saverot, D., "FROM CRIMINALS TO TERRORISTS AND BACK?" Quarterly report: France, 2017

CONCLUSION

If we look at these processes through the prisms of the evolutionary and social psychology, history shows that criminality has always existed, as there were also various forms of terrorism within different borders in different historical periods, societies and the states. Successful examples in our times for societies with low-crime rates are the states of South Korea and Japan and their policy towards the criminals, terrorists and migration.

In a globalized world, the clash of cultures is inevitable, and according to the author of the present study, also a fully necessary to historically produce our collective, human culture that will last as our ultimate form of knowledge as inhabitants of the earth and to reach that, which the American political scientist and economist Francis Fukuyama, defined as the "end of history"¹².

If we look at the same processes through the prism of personal psychology, we see that **It is not possible to adapt the anti - social or marginalized members of our society forcefully, even if we create the necessary factors and conditions, we always come to the factor of their free will.** For example, the situation in the highly social and economically rich Scandinavian countries can be considered as a good climate for a living with a supportive state system, but there are still anti-social behavior and marginalized society members who are at risk of radicalization and recruiting from TG and OCG.

In contrast to fighting crime, where the strengthening of police measures and the return forms of aggression against aggression gives results, with fighting terrorism, this high force methods against the other minded only recruit new members among their lines and create martyrs who popularizes them, as it is shown by the historical experience. While the militarization of the police and the uncompromising action against the criminal contingent, according to the author of this paper and its assessment of historical processes gives results, the same in counter-terrorism will give the opposite. Due to the variety of radical elements and profiles, the significant result in countering and detecting terrorist cells and groups comes from evaluating and studying the information, in which method the results are least negative to the society and the affected risk groups (like immigrants) and innocent members around them. This means that solving the problem requires a more sophisticated and specialized approach that intelligence services and reconnaissance units can offer in the specialized government security structures.

If we can generalize the two strategic approaches, for fighting the OCG, the state can operate and utilizes more drastic and uncompromising, aggressive measures against the criminal syndicates and families, the mafia. Let's say metaphorically, to use a machine gun. But this approach cannot be used against TG, where members emerge from more sensitive parts of society like minorities, religious groups and etc. There the state must utilize perfect precision or it risks to fuel more of the already started radicalization process and empower the TG. In this manner, show of force is counter-productive and the state can't be a machine gunner no more, in fighting the TG the state must operate as a sniper.

If we want to effectively counter both of the threats we can't use the same approach on the strategic level, even if they follow identical psychological models. OCG are more common and known for the security services and the state where most of the perpetrators are already known and were part of the underground life for years, but TG are born and raised in more law-abiding circles, following the same process of individual radicalisation

The answer, the common one to counteract the OCG and the TG is one and it depends on each of us individually and as a state and society members - **to oppose the radical counter-cultures through law, love, compassion, kindness, diligence, charity, selflessness ... The values that have made the Western societies an economic and global political leader. The personal example of civil societies and each of us of kindness to the neighbor, hard work and the contribution of goods to the state and society, persistence and discipline, compassion and mercy, active participation in the social processes and the personal responsibility are the best weapon against radicalization, crime and terrorism.**

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